

Controlling spin textures of magnetic nanodots using an antidot matrix

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We present a study of the magnetic properties of circular nanodots placed inside or in the vicinity of a circular hole in the perpendicularly magnetized antidot matrix. Micromagnetic simulations were performed to investigate the remanent magnetization configurations of the nanodots as a function of their vertical position relative to the matrix. The results demonstrate that the strength of the radial component of antidot matrix stray fields varies significantly along the vertical coordinate. This change influences the remanent state of nanodots, leading, depending on their location, to the stabilization of several magnetization configurations: radial vortex, curled vortex, or single-domain state. It was found that placing the dot at few nanometers below or above the matrix allows to stabilize the vortex state for a nanodot with the smallest diameter. This result provides a hint to tailor the magnetic properties of nanodots for their applications in spintronic and magnonic devices.

Keywords: circular nanodots, antidot matrix, remanent magnetization, spintronic and magnonic devices.

1. Introduction

Recent advances in lithography have enabled the fabrication of magnetic nanoelements with reproducible sizes down to a few tens of nanometers, extendable over large areas [1, 2]. The incorporation of magnetic nanoelements has significantly advanced high-density storage [3], sensitive detection [4], and targeted drug delivery [5]. Arrays of magnetic curvilinear elements (namely circular nanodots) serve as effective ordered pinning centers for vortex lattices in type II superconducting films [6] and play a critical role in magnonics, the field that explores the use of spin waves (magnons) as information carriers [7]. For instance, in Ref. 8, a new type of magnonic crystal was proposed: a magnetic film deposited on a periodic 2D array of circular dots of the

same material. The continuous film serves as a magnonic waveguide when the role of the dot array is to create periodic perturbations of internal fields in the neighbor regions.

Extensive studies on individual nanoelements have revealed that their magnetic properties differ significantly from those of continuous films. Notably, under specific thickness-to-lateral size ratios, circular and square soft magnetic elements can exhibit a vortex state of magnetization, a special type of order consisting of a global in-plane curl of magnetic moments, and a small localized out-of-plane core, which constitutes a topological spin texture [9, 10]. Vortex formation is a fundamental phenomenon observed across diverse systems, ranging from ocean and acoustic waves [11] to electromagnetic whispering gallery modes [12, 13]. Magnetic vortices are important for practical applications

since the vortex cores experience high-frequency oscillations (gyrotropic modes) when displaced from their equilibrium position [14]. As dot thickness increases, higher-order vortex gyrotropic modes have been observed, which are non-uniform along the dot thickness [15, 16]. Recent advances in nano-stencil lithography have allowed for the extension of magnetic vortex configurations into the third dimension [17].

It is important to note that for thin circular nanodots made of soft magnetic materials, a widely studied geometry, the realization of a vortex state is constrained by the dot sizes. For example, a 10 nm thick Permalloy ($\text{Ni}_{80}\text{Fe}_{20}$) nanodot requires a diameter greater than 80 nm to sustain a vortex state; when below this size, a quasi-uniform single-domain state becomes more energetically favorable [18, 19]. Recently, it was demonstrated that dipolar coupling with an out-of-plane magnetized antidot matrix can substantially enlarge the region of the vortex stability in soft magnetic circular nanodots down to 1 nm in thickness and 30 nm in diameter [20, 21]. Using a similar approach, it was also established that artificial magnetic skyrmions, another class of topological spin textures, can be stabilized in a continuous soft ferromagnetic film coupled to a hard magnetic antidot matrix by exchange and dipolar interactions [22]. In all these cases, the main impact was produced by the radial component of the antidot stray field; by varying its strength via a hard layer thickness or/and saturation magnetization it is possible to tune vortex/skyrmion configuration from curled to radial one. Here we extend the study of a soft magnetic dot inside a hard antidot matrix, considering the case when the dot can be shifted vertically within or in the vicinity of the antidot in order to find an optimal position for the formation of a stable vortex ground state in the nanodot of the smallest diameter.

2. Simulation details

To investigate the magnetic behavior of nanodots within an antidot matrix, we performed micromagnetic simulations using MuMax3 v.3.10 software [23]. The object under study is a thin circular magnetic nanodot placed inside or in the vicinity of the hole in a much thicker hard magnetic antidot matrix with lateral dimensions 400×400 nm [Fig. 1(a)]. To minimize the edge effects of the matrix, periodic boundary conditions were applied. The center of the nanodot is aligned with the hole axis. The hard magnetic layer, with thickness t_{HL} (varied from 11 to 31 nm), possesses perpendicular magnetization. The antidot diameter is d_{ad} , while the nanodot, made of soft magnetic material, has a diameter d_d (varied from 40 to 100 nm) and thickness t_d (varied from 1 to 5 nm). For all conducted simulations, a 10 nm difference between d_{ad} and d_d was maintained to prevent direct exchange coupling. The nanodot's vertical position relative to the hard magnetic layer is defined by the parameter ΔZ [Fig. 1(b)], which is the distance between the dot and matrix centers in the vertical direction (i.e., $\Delta Z = 0$ corresponds to the nanodot placed exactly at the antidot center).

Fig. 1. (Color online) (a) A sketch of the considered nanostructure — a soft magnetic nanodot placed within a hole in a hard magnetic layer with perpendicular magnetization. (b) Distribution of stray fields in the antidot; arrow length corresponds to the field magnitude and color to the field radial component B_ρ . The optimal nanodot position (where the radial stray field is maximal) is illustrated.

For a soft magnetic material, we used the following Permalloy parameters: a saturation magnetization $M_s = 8.1 \cdot 10^5$ A/m and an exchange stiffness $A = 1.05 \cdot 10^{-11}$ J/m. The hard magnetic layer parameters were $M_s = 10^6$ A/m and $A = 2 \cdot 10^{-11}$ J/m. The key characteristic of the hard layer is the saturation magnetization; so its out-of-plane magnetic anisotropy was set high enough to ensure stable perpendicular saturated magnetization (i.e., an absence of stripe domain structure) at zero field. Our simulations confirm that the selected parameters resulted in a stable, quasi-uniform out-of-plane magnetization in the matrix after perpendicular saturation. The mesh cell size was either $2.5 \times 2.5 \times 1$ nm (for dots > 50 nm) or $1.25 \times 1.25 \times 1$ nm (for smaller nanodots).

The perpendicularly magnetized hard layer generates magnetostatic stray fields with radial (B_ρ) and perpendicular (B_z) components. In the lateral dimensions, B_ρ is maximal near the antidot edges and is zero in the center, while with the vertical direction, B_ρ varies from identical zero at $\Delta Z = 0$ (vertical center of the antidot) to maximal positive or negative values, which are achieved near the top and bottom surfaces [Fig. 1(b)]. To obtain the remanent states of the nanodots, we followed a specific procedure. First, the nanodots were perpendicularly saturated by applying an external field of $B_z = 1.2$ T. Then, this field was gradually reduced to a small negative field of $B_z = -0.15$ T before being returned to zero. This approach enables the controlled formation of a vortex remanent state at zero external field, as detailed in [20]. To verify whether the remanent vortex state is also the ground state, we compared its total energy at zero external field with that of a single-domain state, which was manually initialized and relaxed to a local energy minimum.

3. Results and discussion

We started our studies with the configuration where the nanodot and the antidot matrix are placed on the same surface [Fig. 1(a)]. This corresponds to $\Delta Z = (t_{HL} - t_d)/2$. Depending on the geometric parameters of the system, three different remanent states are possible: radial vortex, curled vortex, and single-domain (see Ref. 21 for more details). Figure 2 shows the remanent magnetic state diagrams for three antidot matrix thicknesses (11, 21, and 31 nm) for various nanodot geometrical dimensions. The results indicate that the thicker matrix provides greater vortex stability. Larger dot diameters and smaller dot thicknesses also favor vortex formation. It was also found that the region where the vortex state (blue area in Fig. 2) is the true ground state is smaller than the region where a vortex can be achieved at remanence. However, even outside this region, a vortex can be nucleated in practice by gradually reducing the external field from out-of-plane saturation, as done in the simulations. This occurs because the stray fields from the hole favor the nucleation of a radial vortex, which may subsequently evolve into a curled vortex as B_z stray field component decreases. Due to the presence of an energy barrier between the vortex and saturated states [24], the vortex configuration remains stable at remanence.

Fig. 2. (Color online) Remanent state diagrams for the case when both nanodot and antidot matrix are placed on the flat substrate for different thicknesses of the hard layer: $t_{HL} = 11$ nm (a), $t_{HL} = 21$ nm (b), $t_{HL} = 31$ nm (c). Single-domain state (\blacktriangle), curled vortex state (\bullet), radial vortex state (\blacklozenge). The region, where the vortex state is the ground state, is highlighted in blue.

For all three antidot matrix thicknesses, vortex states can be achieved for sufficiently large dot diameters. For $t_{HL} = 11$ nm, vortex states are not the ground state across the entire range. For $t_{HL} = 21$ nm, the matrix-induced radial field stabilizes radial vortices as the ground state only in the thinnest dots with $d_d \geq 70$ nm. Finally, for $t_{HL} = 31$ nm, radial vortices are the ground state for almost all geometries, except for the smallest diameters and largest thicknesses. Therefore, for further studies, we focused on thicker antidot matrices and $t_d = 1$ nm.

Our primary goal was to identify the optimal nanodot vertical position within the antidot matrix from the point of view of vortex stability, crucial for spintronic applications. We simulated the remanent magnetization configurations for a 90 nm diameter, 1 nm thick dot, while changing the nanodot's vertical position ΔZ for two different t_{HL} , namely 21 and 31 nm. For each simulation, we have calculated the radial stray field component B_ρ at the nanodot lateral edge. As it is seen from Fig. 3, for both hard layer thicknesses $B_\rho(\Delta Z)$ reaches its maximum value (in modulus) at 2 nm above the top and below the bottom edges of the hard layer and completely disappears at $\Delta Z = 0$ (the center of the hard layer). It is expected that the strength of B_ρ dictates the remanent states of the nanodot. As ΔZ sweeps from negative to positive values, for $t_{HL} = 31$ nm we observed a sequence

Fig. 3. (Color online) Radial stray field component B_p depending on vertical coordinate calculated for a 90-nm-diameter dot along ΔZ line depicted in Fig. 1 for $t_{HL} = 31$ nm (left panel) and $t_{HL} = 21$ nm (right panel). The yellow area on the plot represents a dot positioned inside the hard layer matrix. Insets demonstrate different remanent magnetization configurations: (a) “outward” radial vortex, (b) “outward” curled vortex, (c) single-domain, (d) “inward” curled vortex, (e) “inward” radial vortex. Color on the insets represents an angle of in-plane rotation of the magnetization vectors.

of spin textures: (a) radial vortex with outward-directed magnetization, (b) partially “outward” curled vortex, (c) single-domain, (d) partially “inward” curled vortex, and (e) inward-directed radial vortex. The vortex inward/outward orientation is determined by the sign of the radial field. Geometries with a strong radial stray field exhibit a characteristic radial vortex state [Fig. 3(a)] [17], while geometries with a weaker radial field produce an unconventional curled vortex [Fig. 3(b)] or single-domain state [Fig. 3(c)].

It is interesting to note that for $t_{HL} = 21$ nm, the radial vortex configuration transfers directly to a single-domain one without entering a curled vortex state. To clarify this issue, we plotted the system's total energy E for radial vortex and single-domain configurations as functions of ΔZ (Fig. 4). The intersection points between the two plots are in good agreement with points of a radial vortex, namely, a single-domain magnetization configuration change. Regions, where the energy of the vortex state is lower than that of the single-domain state (either outside of the hole or inside but in the vicinity of top and bottom dot edges), are the ones where the vortex state is energetically favorable and thus becomes a ground state configuration.

Taking into account both $B_p(\Delta Z)$ and $E(\Delta Z)$ dependence, we can conclude that the optimal nanodot position is in the point where B_p reaches its maximum, i.e., slightly above the top edge of the hard layer. Importantly, this configuration can be realized in a much more practice-friendly structure: a three-layered circular nanodot consisting of soft layer/non-magnetic layer/hard layer with perpendicular magnetization. Such a hard layer will produce exactly the same stray fields as an antidot matrix, and the goal of a non-magnetic layer is to prevent direct exchange coupling between soft and hard

layers. Additionally, a thin non-magnetic layer will place a soft layer into the region where B_p reaches the maximal value. This configuration offers potential advantages for nanofabrication, allowing one-step patterning of the whole structure, elimination of shadowing effects during the deposition of thin soft nanodot into thick matrix hole, and exclusion of direct contact between soft and hard layers.

To demonstrate the advantages of newly found optimal position of the nanodot, we constructed the remanent magnetization state diagram for the dot positioned slightly above (with a 1 nm gap) the top edge of antidot matrix with $t_{HL} = 21$ nm (see Fig. 5). Compared to the previous

Fig. 4. (Color online) Total energy values, E , for radial vortex and single-domain states as a function of vertical shift ΔZ for a 90 nm diameter and 1 nm thick nanodot inside and in the vicinity of a 21 nm thick antidot matrix. The yellow area represents the antidot matrix.

Fig. 5. (Color online) The remanent state diagram for the dot positioned 1 nm above the antidot matrix with $t_{HL} = 21$ nm. The region, where the vortex state is the ground state, is highlighted in blue.

case when nanodot and antidot matrix are placed on the same flat surface (central panel of Fig. 2), the entire diagram is shifted to smaller diameters by approximately 10 nm. As a result, the vortex ground states become possible for dots with smaller diameters due to the stronger radial field component. For the given geometrical and magnetic parameters of soft and hard layers, it was possible to obtain a radial vortex ground state for a 1 nm thick nanodot with $d_d = 60$ nm.

Finally, we built a remanent state diagram $d_d(\Delta Z)$ for dots with $t_d = 1$ nm in the antidot matrix with $t_{HL} = 21$ nm (Fig. 6). It is clearly seen, that the vortex stability reaches its maximum (vortex ground state for minimal d_d) at $\Delta Z = 12$ nm and then decreases as the spacing between the dot and the matrix increases. This behavior correlates with $B_\rho(\Delta Z)$ dependence shown in Fig. 3. It is important to note, that the stability area above the matrix is larger than inside,

Fig. 6. (Color online) Remanent states of the 1 nm thick nanodot in the vicinity of the edge of a 21 nm thick antidot matrix as a function of vertical shift ΔZ . The matrix edge is shown with an orange line. The region, where the vortex state is the ground state, is highlighted in blue.

again supporting the idea of a circular nanodot consisting of soft layer/non-magnetic layer /hard layer as an optimal structure to obtain radial vortex as a ground state.

4. Summary

In this study, we have demonstrated the effective control of magnetic states in soft magnetic circular nanodots by vertically positioning them within or in the vicinity of a hard magnetic antidot matrix. Via micromagnetic simulations, we showed that the radial stray fields emanating from the antidot matrix plays a crucial role in determining the remanent magnetization configuration of the nanodisks. By varying the vertical position of the nanodot relative to the antidot matrix, we achieved transitions between different magnetic states, including radial vortex, curled vortex, and single-domain configurations. A key finding is the identification of an optimal vertical position that enables the stabilization of the vortex state for the nanodot with the smallest diameter. It was established that placing the dot at a certain distance below or above the matrix provides an additional increase in the vortex stability. This finding can significantly simplify the nanofabrication process of ultrathin nanodots with radial vortex as a ground state. The ability to control the magnetic state of nanodots, particularly the stabilization of vortex states at minimal sizes, opens up possibilities for designing novel spintronic devices, magnonic structures, and high-density storage media. Further research could explore the dynamic properties of these controlled magnetic states and investigate the effects of different geometries and materials.

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Керування спіновими текстурами магнітних наноточок за допомогою матриці антиточок

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Представлено дослідження магнітних властивостей кругових наноточок, розміщених всередині або поблизу круглого отвору в перпендикулярно намагніченій матриці антиточок. Було проведено мікромагнітне моделювання для дослідження конфігурацій залишкової намагніченості наноточок як функції їх вертикального положення відносно матриці. Результати показують, що сила радіального компонента полів розсіювання матриці антиточок значно змінюється вздовж вертикальної координати. Ця зміна впливає на залишковий стан наноточок, що призводить, залежно від їх розташування, до стабілізації кількох конфігурацій намагніченості: радіальний вихор, закручений вихор або однодомений стан. Було виявлено, що розміщення точки на кілька нанометрів нижче або вище матриці дозволяє стабілізувати вихровий стан для наноточки з найменшим діаметром. Цей результат дає підказку щодо адаптації магнітних властивостей наноточок для їх застосування в спінтронних та магнетонних пристроях.

Ключові слова: кругові наноточки, матриця антиточок, залишкова намагніченість, спінтронні та магнетонні пристрої.